

NIGERIA JOURNAL OF TAX STUDIES

VOL. 2 NO. 1, 2014

CONTENTS

ARTICLES

<i>An Assessment of the Contribution of Value Added Tax to the Development of the Nigerian Economy</i>		
Denis Basila		1-11
<i>Providing Tax Education in the 9-3-4 Educational System of Nigeria and its Prospects for National Development</i>		
Kyrian I. Mfam and Sheikh K. Alkali		12-24
<i>Introducing Carbon Tax in Nigeria: Taxation as a Policy Instrument for Environmental Management and Control</i>		
Jirinwayo J. Odinkonigho		25-37
<i>Assessment of Personal Income Tax Administration in Kaduna State</i>		
Lateef O. Mustapha and Simon O. Adeniyi		38-50
<i>Research as a Tool for Driving the Federal Inland Revenue Service Professorial Chairs in Taxation and Tax Law Initiative</i>		
Umaru I. Ahmed		51-64
<i>An Assessment of the Contribution of Pay-As-You-Earn to the Internally Generated Revenue of Kano State</i>		
Ishaq A. Samaila		65-78
* <i>The Challenges of Nigeria's Federal Inland Revenue Service in Tax Revenue Collection</i>		
Isallah Haruna		79-109 *
Instructions to Contributors		110-120

THE CHALLENGES OF NIGERIA'S FEDERAL INLAND REVENUE SERVICE IN TAX REVENUE COLLECTION

Isallah Haruna

Tax Audit Department, Federal Inland Revenue Service, Abuja. E-mail: haruna044@yahoo.com

Abstract

This is a descriptive and qualitative study based on the review of relevant literature and observation methods on the challenges of Nigeria's Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) in tax revenue collection. These challenges include dishonesty of tax officials, adopting FIRS' change processes and core values, and inadequate and incomplete records of business transactions. The challenges create ugly situations including tax revenue corruption, low tax revenue yield and voluntary tax compliance issues as taxes are partly confused, wholly ignored, heavily compromised, tactically avoided, and deliberately or negligently evaded. Recommendations are profiled to the challenges as well as prospects of increasing FIRS' tax revenue collection in the light of present-day economic realities. The paper aims at providing information for use by FIRS, other tax revenue authorities and governments responsible for making laws and regulations to optimize tax revenue collection, and to serve as reference materials for academic research.

Keywords: Tax, Revenue, Federal Inland Revenue Service, Nigeria
JEL Classification: H20; H27.

1. Introduction

The impact of revenue for sustainable national development cannot be overemphasized. From time immemorial, nations have been incurring expenditure on infrastructure, education, health, law and order aimed at improving the quality of life of the people. Every sovereign nation needs to collect revenue from its people, particularly in a democratic system such as Nigeria's and spend same in providing democratic dividends including social and economic objectives to them. Tanzi and Zee (2001:1) opined that "taxation is the only practical means of raising the revenue to finance government spending on the goods and services that most of us demand." Bamidele (2010) noted that the importance of tax revenue as a sustainable source of revenue for government to finance goods and services cannot be overemphasized. Tax as a way of raising

revenue refers to a compulsory levy imposed by the government on the incomes of individuals and companies called taxpayers in a country. Anyanwuocha (1993:182) noted that tax as a concept is more than making the payment of some money compulsory by either the government or its agencies and includes "the collection of, and the accounting for, the levied amount and keeping and auditing of records". Taxation is the use of tax tools to collect tax revenue from taxpayers.

In Nigeria, FIRS is empowered to collect the following tax types as tax revenue on behalf of the Federal Government: (1) Oil Tax Revenue essentially from Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT), and (2) Non-oil Tax Revenue essentially from Companies Income Tax (CIT), Value-added Tax (VAT), Capital Gains Tax (CGT) of companies, Personal Income Tax (PIT) of individuals in employment or individuals who are carrying on their own small businesses under a business name or partnership and residents of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), and highly mobile federal workers such as staff of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and other Nigerians and foreigners outside the country but earning income in Nigeria (non-residents), expatriate workers residents in Nigeria, Police Affairs, Military officers and civilians working in the police and military formations. Other non-oil taxes are Education Tax of companies, stamp duties of companies, Information Technology Development Levy, and Withholding Tax (WHT) of companies.

Of course, both oil and non-oil tax revenue collections in Nigeria have never been without stimulating problems referred herein as challenges. Although observations revealed FIRS has been meeting its oil tax revenue targets over the years, it has not been meeting its targets on non-oil tax revenue for the past two or more years in succession owing to some challenges. For instance, Chuke (2011) noted that FIRS collected N1,303.46trillion of non-oil revenue in 2010. This amount was N124.54trillion below the year's government target of N1,428.00trillion. However, in the light of the challenges facing the FIRS, it has been meeting federal government annual revenue targets over the past three or more years in succession.

This paper adopts the descriptive and qualitative study approach and focuses on the tax revenue challenges of FIRS. It profiles recommendations to the challenges as well as prospects of increasing tax revenue collection, particularly non-oil tax revenue. While the paper is not intended to carry out quantitative analysis of FIRS tax revenue collection over the past years, it provides information for use by FIRS, governments and other tax authorities responsible for making laws, guidelines, policies and rules to improve tax revenue collection for national development. Furthermore, the paper will serve as good reference materials for academic research.

2. Literature Review

Challenges of Nigeria's FIRS in Tax Revenue Collection

Tax World (1999) asserts that nobody wants to pay taxes as paying taxes is considered to be a problem by people from time immemorial. Sanni (2010a) opined that Nigerians resist paying taxes because they believe that the tax revenue realized is stolen by government officials. It has been observed that the challenges of FIRS in tax revenue collection are induced by human factors influencing the thinking and decision of tax revenue stakeholders, particularly tax officials and taxpayers. The challenges range from tax compliance issues, corruption of tax revenue to low tax revenue yield as integrity, objectivity and confidentiality are at a premium. The management of FIRS reprehend erring officials and have dismissed some staff in the past. This action is not expected to stop meaning the battle has just begun. Some of the challenges of FIRS in tax revenue collection are discussed in the following subsections.

Adapting to FIRS' change processes and core values

There has been a general notion that change is the only permanent phenomenon on earth. When an organization seeks to improve performance by changing the way it does things in order to improve performance, its employees become the first to resist. This may be followed by other stakeholders too. For instance, since 2004 when the reform agenda of FIRS started, Chuke in Agbo (2011) noted that the attitude of staff has been the greatest challenge in the reform process as people are required to adopt new ways of doing business and a new culture of professionalism and integrity in the work place. A great deal of commitment is required as well as motivation of employees to achieve objectives. The FIRS change processes and core values, namely professionalism, integrity, efficiency and ownership and collective responsibility could be influenced by the following human behavioural variables:

i) **Commitment:** The commitment of tax officials refers to the desire to reasonably perform responsibility qualitatively to achieve the objectives of FIRS. Cole (1993) observed that commitment is an important variable affecting job performance. FIRS wants high-level commitment of members of staff to their engagements. When employees failed, then commitment is said to be low and productivity will be low too. Just as the commitment of FIRS staff must be monitored by management, so the commitment of taxpayers should be monitored by tax officials who come into close contact with them. Tax officials must report whether tax payers are committed to paying their taxes as and when due or not.

ii) **Attitude:** The attitude of tax officials refers to the way they think things should be done in FIRS. Cole (1993) observed that ineffectiveness and inefficiency of transacting parties may be due to their poor attitude in the

business, which gradually erodes organizational policy and culture. Saari and Judge (2004) noted that an important aspect of employee attitude to research in the future will be to focus on the various internal and external environmental factors influencing employee attitudes and emotions at work with a view to understanding the relationship between them. Added to these are customer satisfaction and financial measures affecting employees. Positive attitude is critical for organizational success as it affects an employee's behavioral pattern by modifying his/her thinking. Negative attitude ruins organizational success as it encourages double standards at work, particularly if caused by one form of staff grievance or another.

iii) **Motivation:** Motivation refers to all of the inner drives and striving conditions best described as desires, wishes, etc capable of influencing employees' behavior negatively or positively. There is a view that motivation necessitates the choice between alternative courses of actions for the attainment of pre-determined objectives. Therefore, if employees are not motivated, they would not want to work hard, maintain peace at work and direct their behaviour towards important goal attainment. Hilton (1992) and Cole (1993) observed that motivation plays a significant role in shaping the attitude of employees as well as developing and sustaining compliance with positive work ethics, corporate culture and management support.

Difficulty in tracing taxpayers and the dearth of qualified tax officials

There is the challenge of FIRS' identifying and tracing people and businesses to pay tax owing to the poor or inadequate records of birth, death and business registration as envisaged in Nigeria over the years (Anyanwuocha, 1993). Besides, it has been observed that improper or wrong addresses also increase the difficulty faced by tax officials in the course of discharging their duties. The implication is that tax authorities like FIRS may not be able to know a customer's tax history, nature of business, and office address for tax purposes. As information on a taxpayer is inadequate, it becomes very difficult to establish a reliable or accurate database of taxpayers. Improper addressing of houses is visible in places such as Jikwoyi, Abaji and Zuba in the FCT and makes it difficult tracing addresses of businesses for tax. Also, dead businesses are not reported to FIRS to enable the Service to update its records. While dead businesses remain on record as existing and functional, the problem of non-filers and stop-filers of tax returns is being compounded. Actually, non-filers are taxpayers that have no history or never filed tax returns since the commencement of their business, and stop-filers refer to taxpayers that have a history of filing tax returns before but suddenly stopped filing their returns. Similarly, the dearth of "well-educated and well-trained staff, when money is lacking to pay good wages to tax officials" (Tanzi and Zee, 2001:2) compounds the issue of taxpayers' intelligence

information gathering. Besides, the implication of a dearth of qualified tax officials in FIRS means there may not be sector specialists to be able to adopt measures to increase the number of taxpayers as a window to collect more taxes, particularly in the informal sector.

Inadequate records of business transactions and the informal sector of the Nigerian economy

There are challenges of inadequate and incomplete records of business transactions for tax purposes in Nigeria. In some cases, these records are never kept at all. Anyanwuocha (1993:190) noted that "accurate records of business transactions and income are not kept" for tax purposes in West Africa including Nigeria. Low literacy level negatively affects the keeping of business records and even in situations where such records are kept, they are mostly found to be inaccurate. The implication is that proper tax cannot be collected because correct assessment is not visible. Similarly, the writer observed that the lack of accounting and business knowledge as well as deliberate intention not to prepare, maintain and keep accounting books and records of business activities for tax purposes are prevalent in Nigeria. The informal sector takes the lead as it includes self-employed persons engaged in street hawking such as kola nuts and cigarettes, suya, akara, koko, and sugar cane sellers who in addition to being unable to read and write have no accounting or bookkeeping knowledge. According to Egwaikhede (2010), the informal sector of the Nigerian economy is substantial and causes loss of revenue to the government. As the sector consists of small and medium-scale businesses which are not registered for tax purposes (Tax Audit Headquarters, 2005), this situation compounds the problem of identifying transaction types and items. The lack of records also makes it difficult for tax officials to determine chargeable profit for tax purpose. Although this action is illegal and may be considered a plan to evade tax, it is important for taxpayers to know that ignorance of the law is not an excuse not to pay tax. Furthermore, it has been observed that where taxpayers in the informal sector claim to have records, they prefer to give inaccurate and false information to tax officials in order to reduce their tax liability. This challenge is more visible where most workers in Nigeria do not spend their money in large stores and supermarkets keeping records of sales and inventories accurately for tax purposes. For instance, VAT and PIT may be difficult to assess as sources of employment in developing countries including Nigeria are agriculture or small informal enterprises whose transactions are principally carried out in cash that is off the books and often fluctuate (Tanzi and Zee, 2001). They further observed that financial limitations in developing countries affect the capabilities of tax authorities to generate reliable statistical data that can be used for policy making.

Difficulty in determining the true value of commodity for tax

There are challenges determining the true value of commodities for tax purposes. This applies to commodities that are kept in the form of gold, diamond, precious stones, grains, tubers, and other assets in hidden places (Anyanwuocha, 1993). This may be referred to as stock holding. While quantifying these commodities for tax purposes poses a challenge to tax officials. Sometimes, if and only if the commodities were quantified, the tax assessment may be difficult as no tax rate is provided in the tax law. As a result, it has been observed that the best of judgment (BOJ) rule may be applied leading to the taxpayer paying low or high tax. Again, this depends on the cost that was used to quantify the commodity, which is either the historical cost or market cost of the commodity. Again, the Nigerian economy is poor with a greater number of people depending on subsistence production for family use against commercial production for sales to make gains. The challenge here has been finding solutions to how to tax gains and income from subsistence production that are not estimated for tax but already at the hands of owners. While income from commercial production is highly estimated for tax in the country, it is important to know that commercial activities are decreasing owing to infrastructural decay and neglect. Proactive decisions must therefore be made before any ugly situation arises such as non-oil revenue crash.

Dishonesty by tax officials on duty

The tax officials might demonstrate dishonesty in the discharge of their duties. This could be done by asking for and collecting bribes from taxpayers during official assignments to compromise tax liabilities "in place of the actual amount they [taxpayers] are supposed to pay" (Anyale, 2003:153). Also, tax officials may connive with taxpayers to aid and abet either tax evasion or avoidance and in some cases the two. Sami (2010a:1) noted that "tax payment in various parts of the country is easily manipulated. Tax officials double as consultants to whoever wants to evade tax; they help them to compromise the books and they collect a handsome fee for their services", thus manipulating tax payment. This is fraudulent and unethical. It is important to know that where taxpayers refuse to comply or have actually complied, the outcome may lead to one of: over-assessment, under-assessment or arbitrary assessment of taxpayers, particularly where BOJ is applied (Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria, ICAN, 2009). As the saying goes, familiarity breeds contempt and the fact remains that breaches of ethical tax issues between FIRS tax officials and taxpayers are occasioned by the degree of familiarity between the parties concerned.

Insecurity and attack on tax officials

Another challenge is that tax officials are under attack. They are insecure and may entertain fear in the ordinary course of their assignments. While there are cases of threats, attacks on and death of FIRS staff across Nigeria, the prevalent cases of

insecurity of FIRS staff topped the agenda at a North Central Regional Enlarged Management Meeting in Kogi State. During the meeting, "Okauru urged participants to take a critical look at the issue of insecurity as regards kidnapping and information sharing in order to ensure a secure and fair environment to operate" (Ikosin, 2010b:15). This is wholly because taxpayers are yet to acquaint themselves with the activities of government, particularly the issue of spending tax revenues to provide social and economic amenities for quality life, and to support business activities in the country. Again, as taxpayers are becoming disillusioned by the day and express their anger over lack of electricity, potable water, good roads, healthcare etc, they protest and resort to violence against tax officials because they feel FIRS is the custodian of government revenue as the organization collects it. Olaofe (2008:11) noted that in communities without social amenities, tax officials are afraid and "find it difficult explaining to such taxpayers why they should continue to pay tax". Similarly, Ochei (2008:1) noted that "tax administrators go through very difficult times, trying to assess and collect tax. They are sometimes manhandled, ruffled, or even beaten up in the course of duty". Furthermore, the less privileged taxpayers feel bad and behave wild. Sanni (2010b:1) noted that "the rich in Nigeria enjoy privileges that they do not deserve, the unfairness of which provokes the poor and is partly at the root of social violence and alienation" affecting further tax revenue drive. Or partly because taxpayers have lack of or inadequate knowledge of tax as their civil responsibility making them apathetic to paying taxes. Rather, they consider tax evil and a drain on their incomes and try to evade it at all cost.

Political influence and corruption of tax revenue

There is the challenge of political influence, which is an extension of the democratic value system. This is exhibited by government officials, particularly at the top level, where an executive may use some form of power to announce and prohibit some individuals and companies from paying tax on some transactions, without regard to the tax revenue implications. The waivers may be in the form of import waivers, which in some cases are granted to favour certain taxpayers only. The aftermath of waivers should be the point of greatest concern as they significantly reduce government tax revenue. While political leaders, including Presidents, actually pay income tax as routine civil obligations in developed countries such as the USA, the situation is different in Nigeria, as some people appear to live above the law and do not pay income tax (Sanni, 2010a). It has been observed that this situation applies to the rich and high net-worth individuals (HNIs) who live in high-class areas too. The rich people always want to either directly or indirectly evade tax in Nigeria using "their positions and/or connections to see them through" (Olaofe, 2008:11). However, the uneven income distribution in the country means the rich should be heavily taxed. But the rich taxpayers have access to and use political and economic power to influence

tax reforms likely to increase their tax burdens. This explains the reason PIT and CGT among other taxes are yet to be fully exploited and maximized in Nigeria. Worst still is the inability of political leaders to spend tax revenue judiciously to provide democratic dividends to citizens. Ikosin (2010a:46) noted that "participants at the [Annual Tax Conference say] people certainly will resist paying taxes if government at all levels are not making judicious use of income generated from taxation". Oloafe (2008), Anyaele (2003) and Anyanwuocha (1993) noted that when tax revenue collected from taxpayers ended up in tax officials' and political leaders' pockets by way of corruption, taxpayers will always refuse to pay taxes as they do not see the benefit of doing so.

Transfer pricing challenge

Another challenge is finding a solution to the problem of transfer pricing in international tax. As related companies transact business with each other, the prices charged for the exchange of goods and services between them may not be in an arm's length termed transfer mispricing. Fowokan (2011:64) described a transfer price as "a price set by a taxpayer when selling to, buying from, or sharing resources with a related person (associated enterprise, related party)". Taxjustice Network (2005) argued that transfer pricing in itself is not illegal and abusive but transfer pricing manipulation is illegal. The Network reports 60-70 per cent of world trade takes place within multinational companies (MNCs) and their associate enterprises. Davidmann (2006) recognized transfer pricing as one of the most controversial and least understood operations of multinational companies because this is done to shift profits from one high-tax jurisdiction to a low-tax jurisdiction. The aims include profit maximization by tax avoidance and by obtaining tax rebates, while the tax burden of this gimmick is being carried out by other taxpayers. Nigeria like other developing countries suffers transfer pricing gimmicks arranged by MNCs and the country is losing huge amounts of tax revenue. Onyeukwu (2007:2) noted that "there is an absence of clear transfer pricing regulations" in Nigeria. Again, the dearth of transfer pricing specialists in FIRS compounds this problem in the country. Sheppard (2010) noted that non-governmental organizations believe the developing countries are worst hit by the effects of transfer pricing, as they lose as much as \$160billion of tax revenue yearly because they lack the technical and administrative resources to tackle the activities of the well-represented MNCs.

Administrative bureaucracy/bottlenecks and inadequate logistics

There is the challenge of administrative bureaucracy which delays approval for execution of assignments within departments and even groups. Sometimes issues requiring the FC's approval may be delayed or may not be presented causing tax officials and indeed taxpayers to either support or not support an effective and efficient tax administration. Issues under consideration include tax officials'

grievances being expressed from time to time in respect of the culture and policy of the organization and their expectations. Common issues include training, promotion, transfer, health, working tools and transport. Olaofe (2008) noted that working materials including vehicles are inadequate for tax officials to go out for tax drives. Where there are few vehicles available, bosses take and keep them strictly for their personal errands and allow official jobs to suffer. The issue of inadequate communication facilities compounds the challenges of FIRS tax revenue collection. For instance, the intercom service to link tax officials with their colleagues as well as taxpayers is not effective. Delay in the supply of stationery and the printing of tax leaflets contributes to poor tax yields as information dissemination is being tampered with. Besides, it has been observed that infrastructure, particularly FIRS' buildings, designed and decorated in the organization's colour, style and logo in different parts of Nigeria, is lacking. The FIRS rents buildings to use as offices but pay huge amounts of money as rent. Further, the bureaucracy involved in applying for and processing tax refunds may cause disenchantment among taxpayers who may refuse to apply for tax refunds or generate tax compliance issues in the first instance.

Slow pace of computerization and poor Internet connectivity

Another challenge is the slow pace of the computerization, networking and poor Internet connectivity of FIRS tax offices in the country. The computer and the Internet support electronic mails delivery where the parties involved are information technology compliant. Also, they grant access to FIRS web page to permit all tax transactions in the comfort of the taxpayers' offices and rooms as well as tax officials' too. Okengwu in Agbo (2011:28) noted that the FIRS web portal is a new product posing challenges including "failure in connectivity and electricity supply which makes it difficult to serve [FIRS] customers" as required. Similarly, in an interview with Agbo, Faozat Ogunniyi noted that the FIRS Internet requires expansion of bandwidth to improve performance. Again, tax officials' access to the FIRS web portal seemed to be low as some officials do not even know that the organization has a web portal to facilitate tax compliance research including ascertaining tax payments by tax types, corporate bodies and individuals at any point in time. This is being compounded by the Internet banking system in Nigeria, which is yet to be fully compatible with e-banking transactions beyond checking balances and making transfers as well as paying other bills different from tax liabilities as in countries such as Australia, the USA and the UK. Again, it has been generally observed that computerization and Internet connectivity in Nigeria affect the spread of information and communication from tax officials to taxpayers and vice versa. This challenge has been attributed to poor postal services, which make tax officials wonder whether their correspondence actually reaches taxpayers or not. Courier services are available but at a higher cost to the tax officials and taxpayers. Furthermore, the

global system for mobile communication (GSM) service providers such as MTN, Airtel, GLO and Etisalat operating in Nigeria are expected to facilitate the exchange of information between tax officials and taxpayers, but customers experience network failure and problems of interconnectivity. Over the years, the quality of their services has been questioned by customers and the government on grounds of high tariffs and poor service delivery for prepaid subscribers, and in relation to their reported turnovers.

Incorrect rates of taxes used and activities of FIRS collecting agents

There are challenges of wrong or incorrect rates of taxes such as PAYE, VAT and WHT charged on taxable amount of employment income, contract in respect of supplies and services; the non-deduction of WHT and VAT from supplies and services; and the non-remittance or delay in remittance of the taxes deducted at source such as VAT, WHT and PAYE by collecting agents. According to Olanfe (2008:11), taxes deducted at source suffer "timely remittance to relevant tax authority". It has been observed that other challenges include the payments of PAYE, VAT and WHT lumped together and paid using one cheque or e-payment mandate with or without payment schedules or the payment schedules available may not be self-explanatory and very difficult to understand. In some organizations, particularly the ministries, departments and agencies (MDAs), contracts of supplies and services are given to staff members, friends or relatives without regard to company registration with the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC), and taxes (WHT and VAT) may not be deducted from such transactions.

False declaration of incomes and/or expenses manipulations

The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN, 2009) documented that some companies manipulate records to either understate their incomes and/or overstate their expenses to evade tax. In some cases, companies deliberately engage in the omission of a chargeable income from their tax returns by creating and maintaining secret accounts and reserves hiding them from tax officials. Again, taxpayers, particularly companies, may take advantage of loopholes in tax laws to avoid tax payments or raise issues of claims for allowances and reliefs likely to be false. This situation must not be condoned and should be subjected to tax audit. Besides, Anyanwueha (1993) and Anyaele (2003) noted that the high incidence of tax evasion and tax avoidance may be due to false declaration of taxable income, particularly by self-employed individuals and small private firms. This is done to make them pay less tax in most cases and they scale through sometimes but not all the time.

Delay in reviewing tax laws and their ascends

There is the challenge of reviewing and updating tax laws as well as seeking approval for assent. The difficulty of reviewing and updating tax laws as a result

of weak support by the National Assembly caused by delay in speedy reading and passage of tax bills and the delay in assenting to such bills into laws affect their operations. Quadri in Emmanuel (2011:1) noted that "the various houses, both at the federal and state levels, should create House Committees on Taxation and Revenue to fast-track the ongoing reform agenda of the tax system". While Quadri has appealed to the National Assembly for passage of the outstanding bills before it, it has been observed that where the lawmakers feel a tax bill if passed into law will not favour them and the rich, they veto it. This is not proper for an effective and efficient administration of tax in Nigeria. For instance, Sanni (2010b:1) adduced that, for over 10 years now, there has been reform on tax administration in Nigeria. "But the reform seems to be more of a pro-rich proposition in its design and implementation, creating a regime of unfairness and unequal opportunities" because it appears that only the Nigerian worker is still managing to pay taxes. He argued that the pay as you earn (PAYE) system ensures that only the over-worked and under-paid workers pay their taxes while the rich and political class stay relaxed. According to Sanni (2010a:2):

The Joint Tax Board (JTB) has, in the last few years, talked about tax reform and a more equitable system, but the National Assembly has been slow in considering the New Tax Policy Bills. [He argues that] any proposal, however, which sustains the tradition of multiple taxation and further harassment of the poor, while the rich manipulate the system and gain tax breaks cannot address existing loopholes.

This is a serious issue as, without the law, taxation will not be effective because tax disputes are hinged on legal rights. In addition, Sanni observed that the lawmakers in Nigeria do not check strictly the tax status of nominees for public positions. In the 2007 elections, the JTB wanted tax payment to be a requirement for public appointments. It observed that most politicians presented fake tax certificates and even took the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) to court on this ground but not even one person was sanctioned.

Resistance by FIRS staff to proceed on transfer

Another challenge is that FIRS staff members hardly accept posting when transferred from one location to another. It has been observed that some staff prefer to overstay in offices claiming that such places are good for them because they make illegal deals to make money. Such staff lobby and even bribe personnel officers not to transfer them. However, they become very familiar with taxpayers, which may bring contempt and issues of less or no assessment and fraud may come up affecting job performances (ICAN, 2009). Similarly, even when staff accept to proceed on transfers, it has been observed that such staff tend to hide

files of taxpayers they had illegal dealings with. This affects the normal functioning of the office. Closely related to this is the challenge of record keeping of all taxpayers' files and other documents for reference purposes in FIRS offices. This makes access to sensitive information very difficult or even impossible.

Multiple Taxation Issues

PriceWaterCoopers (2010:3) describes multiple taxation as "paying similar taxes on the same or substantially similar tax base" including Companies Income Tax, Education Tax, Information Technology Tax charged on profits, and Sales Tax, Value Added Tax charged on sales. Oluabunwa (2008) noted that these situations make the Federal Government and other tax authorities guilty of double taxation and multiple taxation respectively. While multiple taxation issues have implications including a hike in prices of goods and services customers pay for, it significantly affects the taxpayers who part with more money to different tax jurisdictions. This makes taxpayers take issue with tax authorities in different jurisdictions and call on FIRS to mediate between them as the apex tax authority in Nigeria. For instance, several complaints were received by FIRS from different associations representing taxpayers including Manufacturers' Association of Nigeria (MAN), Association of Licensed Telecommunication Operators of Nigeria (ALTON), and Amalgamated Food Stuff and Cattle Dealers' Association of Nigeria (AFSCDA). The complaints hinge on "extortion of money from their members by revenue officials usually assigned by the state and local governments" (Okereocha, 2011:30). Ikojin (2010c) noted that the 122nd Meeting of the Joint Tax Board (JTB) was based on multiple taxation complaints by taxpayers. Okauru in Mokwa (2011:44) also "expressed displeasure over the non-compliance to resolutions and decisions reached at the [JTB] council meetings". She reiterated the intimation of the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), European Union (EU), and the World Bank on the negative implications of multiple taxation including deterring investment and reducing the international competitiveness of Nigeria in the global market (Oluabunwa, 2008).

Inadequate tax information for taxpayers and quality and number of tax officials

Both tax officials and taxpayers are expected to be knowledgeable about the existing tax laws, principles and practice of taxation. Unfortunately, "most of the taxpayers are ignorant about the existing tax laws and their application in their tax affairs" (Olofofe, 2008:11), because of their low level of education on the different aspects of tax laws. This negatively affects FIRS tax revenue collection as voluntary compliance is lacking and tax evasion has become the order of the day. For instance, where most economic transactions start and end orally without written documents, no stamp duty will be collected because no documents

stamped. Similarly, it has been observed that the timing for tax payments is not very clear to taxpayers either because they forget it or because they feel such payments may be done at any time they desire, which is wrong. All this is a reflection of weak FIRS engagement with taxpayers. Closely related to this is the quality of tax officials employed and deployed to tax offices nation-wide. It has been observed that most tax officials have no strong background in taxation and do not receive adequate in-house training on taxation. This issue is compounded by the small number of tax officials to attend to a large number of taxpayers. It has been observed that FIRS has a staff strength of about seven thousand employees to serve an estimated population of 160 million people in Nigeria. This staff strength is small implying that many tax operations may be left undone or done negligently (Olaofe, 2008).

Inadequate inter-agency collaboration with FIRS

Inter-agency collaborations with FIRS, particularly from the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC), Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), Ministry of Justice, Independent Corrupt Practices and Other Related Offences Commission (ICPC), and commercial banks are imperative for establishing and sustaining an efficient tax system, particularly concerning tax audit and criminal investigation (Bob Osaghae 2012). Inter-agency collaborations will facilitate information-sharing for the purpose of tracking taxpayers. According to Olaofe (2008:11):

Almost all other government departments will have one thing or the other to do with tax boards. Unfortunately, there is no coordination of activities of these departments that could have assisted the boards to build up an up-to-date database

Ineffective inter-agency collaborations distort adequate and full audit trial of taxpayers.

Poor Accountability and Corporate Governance

Accountability was described by Okwoli (2005) as a management system with responsibilities and resources assigned to an organization's officials, and they are responsible for reporting objectives, performances and achievements; for the purpose of justifying their actions or receive sanctions for inactions as a result of their misconduct. It has been observed that accountability is lacking in public sector including FIRS in Nigeria. The implication is that staff may be mismanaging resources, using public assets for private use such as official vehicles without permission or discussion with tax authorities. According to Ghartey (2004), corporate governance is the system an organization is directed and controlled to achieve objectives. This involves decisions on human and

resource management for public concern (Plumptre and Laskin, 2003). Kellerhais (2009), Stovall, Neill and Perkins (2004) noted that corporate governance remains the only key to economic development, especially in the developing countries including Nigeria. As Sapovadia (2004) noted, poor governance and right or wrong decisions by management, successful or unsuccessful monitoring, direction, controlling and decision review by an organization's directors and stakeholders in the tax system may not allow FIRS to perform well. Although Manzoni and Islam (2009) noted that poor performance in public service including FIRS may be compounded by the complexity of people and multiple objectives, they observed that corporate governance provides a very important aspect of evaluating performance. The implications of poor accountability and corporate governance include lack of openness, integrity, objectivity and transparency resulting in embezzlement, theft, fraud, gross misconduct and corruption of tax revenue.

Tax evasion and tax avoidance issues

At this juncture, it should be noted that the above challenges give birth to two other issues, namely tax evasion and tax avoidance. Arogundade (2010:480) documented that:

The traditional approach to the discussion of the concept of tax planning is to differentiate between tax evasion and tax avoidance. Both have the common effect of revenue minimization but the difference is invariably linked to the means. Tax evasion is viewed as achieving the tax minimization through illegal means whereas tax avoidance achieves the same end through lawful means.

It has been observed that no tax system can be effective and efficient if tax evasion and tax avoidance are prevalent. Olofe (2008) provided a clear difference with actionable examples between the two. According Olofe, tax evasion is an:

Outright or deliberate breaking of law to minimize or not to pay taxes at all...also involve deliberate falsification of records, concealment of information, understatement of profits, inflating expenses, etc (p.12).

Two types of tax evasion were identified for tax officials to understand: total evasion (when a taxpayer has fully escaped payment of taxes) and partial evasion (when a taxpayer reduced the amount of taxes paid through illegal actions). On the issue of tax avoidance, Olofe (2008: 12) noted that it involves:

Manipulating of tax rates, carrying out business activities under a more tax-friendly form of ownership, capitalization of income,

entering into a leasing arrangement, manipulating one's residency status and acquiring business with previous heavy claimable losses all with a view to reducing tax liabilities.

Both tax evasion and tax avoidance reduce tax revenue yield to the government. Therefore all tax authorities frown on these activities and have criminalized them, particularly tax evasion offences.

Prospects of improving FIRS' Tax Revenue Collection

There are prospects of increasing FIRS' tax revenue collection and the following could be considered and improved upon:

Staff training to be systematically organized and intensified

Training of FIRS staff on compliance and enforcement, particularly tax audit, monitoring and tax investigation in this era of self-assessment will significantly improve their job performances and increase the tax revenue collection of FIRS. Self-assessment requires taxpayers to compute their tax liability and file tax returns on their own, with less pressure from the revenue authorities (Onyegbule, 2011). Experiences of developed countries including Japan and the USA reveal that the self-assessment system has been made "a key component of their tax systems [and] tax enforcement is only used sparingly on occasions where there are defaulters" (Deji and Onoja, 2011:8). This reveals that the voluntary compliance of taxpayers in Nigeria can only be improved and successful if compliance and enforcement by tax officials are adequate, strong and reliable. Similarly, all training programmes should be intensified and organized to cut across the entire staff of the organization based on functional areas aimed at sector specialty to cover areas posing a serious threat to FIRS such as transfer pricing, VAT and the taxation of informal sector businesses. The suggested training format below is worthy of consideration:

- i) Staff members on different salary grade levels should know the kind of training scheduled for their respective levels every year.
- ii) Inland Revenue Number should be the basis for running the training downwards in that order for all categories of staff.
- iii) Every employee should attend the same number of training programmes in a year, depending on grade levels.
- iv) Time and venue of training should be communicated directly to participants through e-mail addresses and GSM numbers maintained by the Human Capital Management and Development Department.
- v) Training benefits such as transport and duty tour allowance should be paid to training participants to boost their morale preferably two days to the commencement of the programme. Financial benefits should be received before departure for training.

Strict compliance with FIRS tax revenue policy objectives

There should be strict compliance with the tax revenue policy objective of FIRS. The purpose of the revenue policy objective is to encourage FIRS to double its efforts in meeting tax revenue targets as well as exploring other tax revenue opportunities where there is legislation. There should be strict observance of disciplinary measures, including penalties and interest on defaulters of tax revenue collectible by FIRS. Also, the application of the relevant provisions in tax laws and the FIRS Establishment Act, 2007 on erring stakeholders should be strongly adhered to. The aim is to eradicate intended tax revenue corruption, evasion and fraud by tax officials and taxpayers.

Complete automation of FIRS' tax revenue collection process

It is practically important for FIRS to automate its tax revenue collection process in sum total. This can be achieved by adopting and enforcing the use of taxpayer identification code and number and establishing a taxpayer database to facilitate compliance risk assessment, e-revenue payment system and electronic tax assessment. Therefore, a strong and reliable web portal and Internet connectivity is necessarily required for use by tax officials and taxpayers. Although the Integrated Tax Administration System (ITAS) Project is a step in the right direction, it has not fully taken off. Efforts by FIRS and the government should be geared towards the timely completion and proper take-off of the ITAS project.

Actual and full implementation of government's annual budget

Government should implement its annual budget strictly to the maximum in order to provide infrastructure and achieve social and economic objectives such as electricity, roads, health and education for the purpose of providing quality life to the people. Nwachukwu (2009) informs that the right balance between revenue generation and utilization can best be achieved through budget implementation as a country caters for its citizens. Again, when people have access to quality life, they will be very happy doing business and taking paid jobs as well as appreciating paying their taxes to the government.

Acquaint staff with office organizational methods

FIRS should organize retreats on office organization methods, office procedures and filing systems to update staff on how to prepare and arrange documents in taxpayers' files, particularly tax audit and assessment files. Better still the programme should be incorporated into the Preliminary Inspectors of Taxes Course for tax practitioners to give staff the opportunity of acquiring office management and filing skills. The aim is to make FIRS staff proficient in office management and filing system as well as to understand that sensitive documents and information are not to be tampered with in tax offices. Also, methods of reception and proper handling of taxpayers by showing courtesy to them because

they are kings should be taught to tax officials. This is to warmly invite the taxpayer to freely come forward to pay taxes as and when due.

3. Recommendations for Increasing FIRS' Tax Revenue Collection

In view of the challenges considered above, FIRS must intensify efforts to collect tax revenue from its existing taxpayers and to bring into its tax net more taxpayers. The following recommendations will improve FIRS' tax revenue collection:

1. Human beings are the greatest assets of an organization and need to be adequately taken care of at all times. According to Tella, Aycmi and Popoola (2007:1):

The management of people at work is an integral part of the management process. To understand the critical importance of people in the organization is to recognize that the human element and the organization are synonymous. A well-managed organization usually sees an average worker as the root source of quality and productivity gains. Such organizations do not look to capital investment, but to employees, as the fundamental source of improvement. An organization is effective to the degree to which it achieves its goals. An effective organization will make sure that there is a spirit of cooperation and sense of commitment and satisfaction within the sphere of its influence. In order to make employees satisfied and committed to their jobs in [tax revenue collection], there is need for strong and effective motivation at various levels, departments, and sections of the [FIRS].

While motivation is a significant element of behaviour, attitude directly impacts on job satisfaction that may be caused by commitment. Specifically, commitment, attitude and motivation of FIRS staff need improvement in the light of present-day economic realities as follows:

1. The commitment of tax officials in FIRS should be improved. Benefits and incentives should be provided to the qualified and most appropriate persons with professional knowledge and membership of credible professional institutions to encourage handling of tax revenue matters in professional capacity. Rules should be set to govern the activities of tax officials and such rules should be reviewed regularly.
2. The attitude of tax officials in FIRS should be improved. Staff grievances and financial measures as well encouraging and sponsoring all staff to

attend workshops, seminars, training and conferences to enable them to acquire or update their knowledge and skills are very necessary. Attitude can best be improved through systematic training and re-training and catering for the organization's members' motives, needs, etc.

3. The motivation of tax officials in FIRS should be improved. Incentives should be reasonable and valuable to staff in order to energize them to work as well as prevent financial embarrassment. Therefore, the pay package should be enhanced to reduce tax revenue corruption, particularly bringing the package at par with other revenue-generating organizations making contributions behind FIRS into the federation account in the country.
4. Streets and houses within the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) tax jurisdiction should be named and numbered to facilitate registration and tracing of business names, realize new businesses given birth, and ascertain dead businesses. High-network Individuals (HNIs) and other rich people can easily be traced and audited through correct addresses. In addition, government should have a town development plan with adequate layouts to encourage businesses as well as allow for the interplay of entrepreneurs, facilitate tax drive by the tax officials and permit free movement of people and goods. Furthermore, markets and shops should be provided by the government either through public-private partnership or sole sponsorship to organize business people for tax purpose. If knowing the taxpayers and the nature of their business will help to improve tax administration in Nigeria, it means that, with a good town plan, shops and market sites, the activities of people in the informal sector will be captured and people made to pay taxes on their incomes.
5. Tax laws provide that accounting books should be maintained by taxpayers, where their detailed transactions would be recorded for tax purposes. Taxpayers should exhibit maturity by simply complying with laws voluntarily. Because claiming ignorance of the law is not an excuse, taxpayers' refusal to comply with tax provisions should be adequately punished to deter others. Therefore, frequent checks should be carried out by appropriate tax officials on taxpayers' business premises within their tax jurisdictions to monitor compliance with record-keeping. Again, any information supplied by taxpayers must be in writing and should be thoroughly scrutinized and subjected to the tax man's principle of wholly necessary, reasonable and exclusive nature of the information in generating the income of the business or going concern of the business.

6. Information and communication are veritable tools for bridging the knowledge gap. This is because the two make people aware of their duties in the first instance. However, it is advised that cost-effective channels, speed and reliability should be considered when choosing the method of communication to be used. Information should be correct and clear to be easily understood by the recipient. Also, it is good to open files where any information received can be documented for future reference. Again we must always acknowledge receipt of information by sending feedback. In modern business, the GSM and the Internet provide best choices for use because of their speed and reliability. Therefore, computerization and networking of FIRS' offices nation-wide should be intensified in order to ensure that tax officials and taxpayers transact business using the web. This will eliminate situations where FIRS' staff might take official information and documents to cyber cafes to send them to their destinations. There is no choice but to join the information and computer technology crusade to avoid too much paper work.
7. FIRS should recruit professionals who have prior knowledge in tax matters to be able to research and broaden the tax base as well as find a solution to taxing subsistence production rather than raising tax rates and increasing the tax burden on taxpayers and companies' production. Again, staff deployment to tax offices should be done with due regard to professionalism and previous work experience to try to address issues of taxing precious materials such as gold, diamond, tubers and others. Also, in this category are commodities held in stock, a common practice in Nigeria. A law may be enacted to specify the period for holding stock which will be tax-free, and the rate of tax to be paid when the commodities were not sold beyond the stipulated period. Dealers will provide information about their clients if motivated.
8. Tax officials in the true and fair discharge of their duties should demonstrate honesty, objectivity, confidentiality, integrity and competence in line with the professional ethics of their various institutes. While tax officials are expected to be incorruptible, following professional etiquettes, taxpayers should be honest in declaring their income for tax purposes, compute and file accurate tax returns in time in any assessment period to avoid penalty and interest. Again, erring officers should be adequately punished including summary dismissal.
9. Taxpayers should persistently be educated in tax matters and on all tax types to enable them to know their tax responsibilities as well as to engage in dialogue with FIRS, where the need arises. The current taxpayer

education system by FIRS, including advertisement jingles and sponsoring programmes on newspapers and television stations, is desirable and with time tax awareness and campaign would be done by taxpayers. When individuals and companies voluntarily pay taxes on their incomes to FIRS, this will reduce overhead cost of tax administration. Although, taxpayers should be made to know the effect of delaying payments of their tax liabilities as a punishable act with penalties and interest, they should know that tax officials only collect tax revenue for the government and do not spend it. Therefore, violence against tax officials should stop and it is better for officials to be security conscious all the time. Furthermore, government should be committed to serving the people better by providing infrastructure, electricity and good roads for instance. This way, taxpayers will be convinced that it is what they pay to the government that is being spent on them. This action will arouse taxpayers' interest to pay taxes in expectation of greater social and economic amenities from the government as well as reduce attack on tax officials. Similarly, FIRS should give special attention to the informal sector of the economy by intensifying taxpayer education. Therefore, the sector may be segmented and meaningful accounting guidelines capable of eliciting voluntary compliance should be developed, publicized, implemented and monitored. While adequate and appropriate infrastructure is required to be put in place to control informal sector activities, Egwaikhife (2010) suggests the introduction of broad-based VAT to cover a wide range of products as a way forward to bring the informal sector into the tax net.

10. Tax laws should be reviewed and updated in order to close the gaps against tax evasion and tax avoidance or establish new rules where there are none. The review should be periodically done say within three years or earlier after their enactments to capture the challenges posed by a changing business world. Again, specific tax rules on areas such as transfer pricing should be made to reduce tax disputes while increasing tax revenue. For instance, while formula apportionment is used in the USA, separate accounting method is used in most parts of the world in line with the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD). The former should be adopted in Nigeria so that companies will be taxed on their combined profits subject to some sharing parameters such sales and people. This is suggested because Nigeria is a consumer economy and provides a very wide market for multinational enterprises. Rather than taxing multinationals based on permanent establishment according to the separate accounting method of transfer pricing, departments can organize brainstorming sessions on different aspects of tax laws to try to recommend changes to them or suggesting areas for anti-avoidance

legislation to reduce tax avoidance by taxpayers. Most importantly, tax laws whenever reviewed and updated should be given speedy passage into law by the National Assembly and assented to by the President to support efficient and effective tax administration in Nigeria.

11. Nigeria needs the political will of the executive to make payment of taxes consistent in their administrations. It is observed that some taxpayers could be given tax waivers without prejudice to the tax implications. While waivers should not be subjectively granted to taxpayers on account of favoritism, it is necessary to contact FIRS for advice before any waivers are granted to taxpayers. Again, tax exemption granted to the political class should be reversed and such individuals made to pay income tax on their salaries. Should this be done, it underscores the equity and fairness principle of an ideal tax system.
12. Administrative bureaucracy can be improved upon by the FIRS management by ensuring that files are passed to eligible officers required to act on them immediately such files are received and recorded in an office. Again, staff issues including grievances should not be delayed but considered as a matter of utmost interest. Matters requiring the attention of the Executive Chairman of FIRS should be communicated appropriately and in time. Furthermore, staff issues should be considered first. Their grievances should be quickly addressed and motivation should be used to win staff interest, boost their morale and change their attitude as well as commitment to work. Also, training is important for the purpose of increasing staff productivity because the challenges of revenue collection daily require knowledge updating or capacity development on various tax issues. Therefore, the organization should improve on the training of staff members. Refunds to taxpayers should be treated in time. Money should be appropriated for this purpose.
13. Tax audit and investigation exercises should be intensified and completed in time. During these exercises, records and accounts should be studied carefully. For instance, relevant documents such as invoices, input VAT, cash books, payment vouchers, operating expenses, etc, should be carefully examined for tax rates and amounts contained in the accounts and changes therein. Attention should also be paid to company performance to make analytical reviews of its performance using the ratio analysis. Of course, poor or extraordinary performance of a company requires tax audit to reveal risk areas. Tax returns should be locked at closely for errors in tax computations, documents and records received from taxpayers. Again, checking for beneficial ownership on the

supporting documents for assets, incomes, liabilities and expenditures to ensure that entries are done in the name of the taxpayer is desirable. Also necessary is checking for rewrite to profit general bad debts, depreciation, expenditure of capital nature on new capital assets and all other expenses not allowed for tax purpose included in the accounts. Furthermore, looking closely at the tax return and accounts for complete and proper adherence to the rules of losses and carrying forward is important. Again, PAYE, WHT and VAT deductions and remittances to FIRS through collecting agencies should be verified for correctness and timeliness as well as claims for refunds, allowances and reliefs by taxpayers and the accounts of taxpayers with nil returns or continuous losses in business. Furthermore, it is imperative to carry out risk assessment of taxpayers and pay attention to the industry a company belongs to in order to check group compliance and profitability comparison. Any deviations call for tax audit. Again, unusual requests or extraordinary decisions to centralize or decentralize the operations of a company for audit should be looked at. All of the above would reveal a company's tax compliance level and any manipulations in its accounts. Tax officials in the monitoring and auditing function should refer observations from desk audit for verification and subsequent investigation. Tax audit monitoring exercises revealing deviation of taxpayers and field tax auditors from provisions of tax laws, the establishment act, tax audit manual and tax audit programme should be reported to the FIRS management.

14. The transfer of staff in FIRS should be improved upon. Any employee asked to proceed on transfer must comply and refusal should be sanctioned. Taxpayers' files and other relevant documents must be included in the hand-over notes prepared by the transferred officers, and should be carefully verified by the incoming officers before countersigning the hand-over notes. In case the affected officer is not the one in charge, all his/her work schedules should at the discretion of the Tax Controller (TC) be handed over to another officer immediately. This is aimed at guarding against officers who may proceed on transfer but hide taxpayers' files and other documents. Again, new files opened for taxpayers claiming that old files are lost or on account of an officer being transferred should be investigated and appropriate actions including alerting management should be taken. The existing FIRS transfer policy should be maintained so that no officer spends more than three years in a particular office. This will guide against familiarity between tax officials and taxpayers that brings contempt. Both intra- and inter-regional transfer of staff should be improved in the interest of the organization as well as transfer claims provided to affected staff prior to reporting at a new

station.

15. According to Oluba (2011), FIRS can use data-mining techniques to enhance taxpayers' voluntary compliance because of its potential application in tax administration. In his words:

For instance, predictive modeling will obviously assist the Nigerian FIRS to be in the best position to identify noncompliant taxpayers as well as ensure that tax auditing resources are channeled more appropriately on the accounts that will most likely yield the most desirable tax adjustments (p.1).

The advantages of data mining to FIRS include appropriately harnessing and managing human resources, minimizing wastage of resources on already compliant taxpayers, and modification of traditional audit selection criteria for a scientific one that is sure to produce better results. As tax evasion becomes sophisticated plus high-level corruption in Nigeria, Oluba suggests traditional tax audit to cover taxpayers is outdated and should be replaced with data mining as in the USA, the UK and Australia.

16. FIRS can sponsor the establishment of a tax clinic in the departments of accounting in Nigerian universities. The tax clinic will provide sound training to students as it will allow them to represent taxpayers before the Revenue Service. The aim of the tax clinic is to enable students to gain valuable experience in tax practice and procedure plus earning academic credits. This will strengthen tax education and enable students to develop a strong interest in tax as a career path for the rest of their lives.
17. The FIRS Board should comprise experienced persons, particularly on tax and revenue matters, who are committed and result-oriented with proven integrity as contained in the FIRS Establishment Act, 2007. They should be innovative and creative enough to expand the organization's tax revenue base, as well as ensure an efficient and effective tax system. Similarly, the FIRS management should embrace good governance principles imbedded in Elton Mayor's management principle, which says "others first and self last." This will ensure that staff members are original and key organizational resources that should be treated honorably to support profitable tax administration in Nigeria.
18. A Special Adviser on tax revenue matters should be appointed by the

President subject to critical selection criteria devoid of bias. The ideal person must, in addition to holding a degree in accounting, taxation, economics, law or finance, hold a master's degree and be very experienced in tax matters. The person must have been in full employment of a tax authority, with a career path in tax and served in managerial capacity for not less than 24 months prior to this appointment. Quadri in Emmanuel (2011:1) enjoined both the federal and state governments in Nigeria:

To give special attention to tax matters in their cabinets with the re-introduction and creation of a special office to look into matters that concern the development of taxation at the various levels. [Noting that] part of the strides achieved in Lagos State in terms of improved revenue generation and efficient tax administration system were occasioned partly by the creation of the office of a special adviser on taxation and revenue.

19. FIRS should increasingly organize workshops on its tax revenue collection challenges and invite taxpayers to come and discuss such challenges under structured topics. Transparency and accountability should be observed in information sharing with revenue stakeholders. Opportunities should be taken to advise taxpayers on their civil responsibilities hinged on paying taxes as a right and not as a privilege by citizens and all and sundry. Taxpayers should be free to air their grievances in the forum, and where possible such grievances should be attended to on the spot.
20. FIRS should have a revenue salary structure (REVSS) with a reasonable pay package in recognition of annual inflation rate and present-day economic realities to motivate staff to work harder while shunning corruption. Therefore, FIRS should have revenue rights including the rights of retaining some percentage of revenue collected on all of its tax types. The amount of money retained should be used to service REVSS including staff training and development, bonuses, monthly welfare, allowances (such as educational, medical children transport, meal, utility, wardrobe and dependants), day-to-day administration, reward and other incentives among other expenditure areas. REVSS will significantly improve staff commitment and attitude to work, and at the same time eradicate tax revenue corruption in FIRS and financial embarrassment of staff. Also, it will bring FIRS staff at par with other finance-based organizations such as the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), and other revenue-generating units in the country such as the Nigerian National

Petroleum Corporation (NNPC).

21. FIRS should invest in research and development (R & D) to address tax issues such as transfer pricing, capital allowances and refunds as applicable. Specialists could be trained in these areas owing to the growing nature of businesses in Nigeria. Rules and regulations on transactions and taxes should be developed and have them in place, rather than develop them when issues arise. The idea is to prevent and reduce any tax revenue loss being suffered by the government in Nigeria. Similarly, research to address the tax challenges of FIRS could be sponsored by the organization through the R & D vote and where such a vote exists, it should be well utilized. Again, staff members should be encouraged and sponsored fully for research degrees at the master's and Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D) levels in both local and international universities. Publications are useful in this regard too and should be encouraged.
22. There should be revenue courts strictly for speedy hearing and judgment on tax revenue matters, particularly on areas of tax disputes or appeals between taxpayers and tax revenue authorities as well as between two or more revenue authorities. These courts should be independent of the conventional courts and should have professional judges too. Therefore, efforts should be geared towards the recognition of revenue courts in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria if it is established that the federal high court, which has the jurisdiction to entertain tax revenue issues, is underperforming.
23. Tax audit monitoring of field tax audit units should be intensified. The Tax Audit Processes and Programmes Department (TAPPD) that is in charge of tax audit monitoring of field tax auditors should perform its functions elaborately including maintaining a database of all tax payers, and the status of audit carried on them. For this department to efficiently and effectively carry out its functions and report on time, approval for tax audit monitoring visits to LTOs should be given well in advance, particularly on a quarterly basis in view of the significance of the Department in this era of self-assessment regime. Also, by giving approval for tax audit monitoring visits in advance, the challenge of either late or non approval affecting the principal work schedule of the Department will be addressed to permit large-scale operation. Also, a Risk Management Unit should be created to work in close collaboration with the Monitoring Unit. The unit shall be responsible for carrying out assessment of the degree of compliance risk of companies. Furthermore, adequate training on ratio analysis and risk compliance assessment should

be given to staff deployed to the unit in order to enhance their performance.

24. Multiple taxation issues should be addressed as suggested by Oluabunwa (2008) and modified and presented as follows:
 - Improve the issue of fiscal federalism and the concurrent and residual powers conferred on state governments to impose and collect taxes; by adding a clause regulating the states on the issue of multiple taxation including sanctions in order to fast-track the economic development of Nigeria.
 - Roadblocks on high ways and feeder roads as well as the use of thugs to collect taxes and levies should be eliminated as quickly as possible. Again, sanctions must be put in place to deter erring state governments.
 - Quick adherence and implementation of the resolutions and decisions of the JTB by all state governments must take effect. Unless the JTB is not considered by the state governments as a body facilitating tax resolutions between tax jurisdictions, a multi-state tax commission may be established for the purpose of mediating on multiple taxation issues.
 - Most importantly, the JTB should be empowered to discipline any erring state government that either deliberately or negligently refuses to comply with its resolutions on matters of tackling issues of multiplicity of taxes.
 - State governments should research avenues to expand their tax bases instead of engaging in multiplicity of taxes to deter economic activities.

4. Conclusion

From the foregoing, it seems that tax revenue challenges in Nigeria are going to be without end. This is because they are daily problems as taxpayers' voluntary compliance is very low. It means that FIRS must collect the proper tax at the least cost and bring more taxpayers into the tax net. It is very important to understand that the key responsibilities of FIRS include to assess, collect and account for tax revenue for national development, to establish and grow the tax base and taxpayer database, and to champion tax administration as well as formulate a robust and effective tax policy that is friendly to stakeholders for an efficient tax system. However, these responsibilities can only be achieved with the support of the executive, judiciary and legislative arms of government in Nigeria. Since taxation is about the law, all hands must be on deck by way of collaboration to establish and sustain an efficient tax system. As a rule of thumb, it is wiser to be proactive and to be acquainted with our tax system, particularly its operations, as well as the application of sanctions, interest and penalties to engender voluntary compliance by taxpayers. This in the long run will promote the self-assessment regime, expand the tax base, and increase FIRS' tax net and its tax revenue contribution to the federation account, particularly from both oil and non-oil tax revenues.

References

- Agbo, A. (2011), "Coping with the Hiccups: Despite Visible and Incontrovertible Success, FIRS Still Faces Some Challenges which Successive Administrators should Work to Overcome". In *TELL* Special Publication, November. Lagos: TELL Communications
- Anyaeke, J. U. (2003), *Comprehensive Economics for Senior Secondary Schools*. New Edition. Lagos: A. Johnson Publishers Ltd
- Anyanwuocha, A. I. R. (1993), *Fundamentals of Economics for Senior Secondary Schools*. Onitsha: Africana First Publishers Limited
- Arogundade, J. A. (2010), *Nigerian Income Tax & Its International Dimension*. Ibadan: Spectrum Books Limited
- Bamidele, A. J. (2010), "Revenue Collection Performance Trends: Past, Present and Future". A paper presented at the 2010 Induction Programme for New FIRS Staff, Abuja: A Class Garden
- Chuke, O. (2011), "Performance of FIRS in 2010 and Areas of Focus in 2011". A paper presented at the FIRS 2011 Enlarged Management Meeting, 3rd and 4th February, Abuja: Congress Hall of Transcorp Hilton Hotel
- Cole, A.G. (1993), *Management Theory and Practice*: 4th Edition. London: ELBS (DP Publications)
- Davidmann, M. (2006), "Multinational Operations: Transfer Pricing and Taxation". Retrieved on Thursday August 18, 2011 from <http://www.solhaam.org/articles/cim503.html>
- Deji, O. and Onoja, V. (2011), "Self Assessment Regime: Towards Voluntary Tax Compliance in Nigeria". In *Gauge: A Quarterly Publication of the Federal Inland Revenue Service*, April-June, Abuja: Federal Inland Revenue Service
- Egwalkhide, F. O. (2010), "Taxation and State-Building in a Democratic System". In *Nigerian Taxation Journal*, January-June, Vol.11 NO.1, Lagos: The Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria
- Emmanuel, M. (2011), "CITN Urges Government to Improve on Tax Issue: Advocates Passage of Pending Bills". Retrieved on September 21, 2011

from <http://www.tribune.com.ng/index.php/taxation/>...

- Fowokan, T. (2011), "International Taxation". A paper presented at the Special Training Programme organized by The Chartered Institute of Taxation of Nigeria. Monday 14th – Wednesday 16th November. Lagos: Conference Banquet Hall, National Theatre.
- Ghartey, A. (2004), "Corporate Governance: How is the Accounting Profession Responding to the Demand for Greater Transparency and Good Governance in the Public and Private Sectors of the Economy?" In *The Nigerian Accountant*. July/September. Vol. 35, NO.3. Lagos: Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria
- Hilton, P. (1992), "Using Incentives to reward and motivate employees." In *Personnel Management: The Magazines for Human Resource Professionals*. September. London: Personnel Publications Ltd.
- Ikosin, M. (2010a), "Spend Tax resources judiciously-African Leaders Urged". In *Gauge: A Quarterly Publication of the Federal Inland Revenue Service*. April-June. Abuja: Federal Inland Revenue Service
- Ikosin, M. (2010b), "Okauru cautions tax chiefs on flat assessment". In *Gauge: A Quarterly Publication of the Federal Inland Revenue Service*. April-June. Abuja: Federal Inland Revenue Service
- Ikosin, M. (2010c), "Coalition against multiple taxation". In *Gauge: A Quarterly Publication of the Federal Inland Revenue Service*. April-June. Abuja: Federal Inland Revenue Service
- Institute of Chartered Accountant of Nigeria (ICAN, 2009): *Advanced Taxation Study Pack*. Nigeria: VI Publishers
- Kellerhäus, M. D. (2009), "Obama calls on Africans to claim their future." Retrieved on July 17, from www.america.org/st/peacesec-english/2009/July/20090711113734smstahrellek0.88
- Manzoni, A. and Islam, S. M. N. (2009), "Performance Measurement in Corporate Governance." Retrieved on July 7, 2010 from: <http://www.springer.com/business+&management/operations+research/book/978-3-7908-2169-7>
- Mokwa, B. (2011), "Chairman JTH Lampoons Multiple Taxation...calls for

Uniform Application of Tax Laws". In *Gauge: A Quarterly Publication of the Federal Inland Revenue Service*. January-March. Abuja: Federal Inland Revenue Service

- Nwachukwu, I. (2009). "Striking the Right Balance between Revenue Generation and Utilization." Retrieved on February 12, 2009 from http://www.businessdayonline.com/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=252
- Ochei, B. B. (2008). *The Nigerian Taxman's Book*. Lagos: Pyramid Unit Publishers (educational)
- Obuabunwa, S. I. (2008). "Multiplicity of Taxes and the Cost of Doing Business". In *ICAN Students' Journal*. October/December. Lagos: Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria
- Okereocha, C. (2011). "Addressing Public Criticisms: As part of efforts to build public confidence, the Federal Inland Revenue Service tackles complaints by tax payers". In *TELL-Special Publication*. November. Lagos: TELL Communications
- Okwoli, A. A. (2005). "Accountability Standards and Auditing Practices in Revenue Administration in the Nigerian Public Sector". In *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*. Vol. 1, No. 1. Lagos: Cherry Books
- Olafe, E. O. (2008). "Overview of Tax Administration and the three tiers of Government in Nigeria". In *ICAN Students' Journal*. April/June. Vol. 12 No. 2. Lagos: Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria
- Oluba, M. (2011). "Nigeria's FIRS can continuously triple tax revenue through data mining." February 5. Retrieved on Sunday September 25, 2011 from <http://valuefranteira.com/blog/nigeria%e2%80%99s-firs-can-continuously-triple-tax-revenue-through-dataminingby martinon>
- Onyegbule, C. N. (2011). "Implementing Self-Assessment Tax Regime as the means of achieving Voluntary Compliance". A paper presented at the Preliminary Inspector of Taxes Course. Batch 2. Abuja: L & D Hall, Unity Bank Building
- Onyokwu, H. (2007). "Transfer Pricing in the Nigerian Context". Retrieved on Tuesday September 6, 2011 from <http://works.bepress.com/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?articles=1004&content=h>

umprey_onyeukwu

- Plumpire, T. and Laskin, B. (2003): "From Jeans to Jackets: Navigating the transition to more systematic governance in the voluntary sector." Institute on Governance. Retrieved on September 3, 2005 from <http://iog.ca/publications/jtoj.pdf>
- PriceWaterHouseCoopers (2010): "Nigeria@50: Top 50 Tax Issues". October. Retrieved on Tuesday September 6, 2011 from <http://www.pwc.com/ng/en/pdf/top-50-tax-issues.pdf>
- Saari, M. L. and Judge A. T. (2004): "Employee Attitudes and Job Satisfaction." Retrieved on Wednesday September 21, 2011 from <http://www.utm.edu/staff/mikem/documents/jobsatisfaction.pdf>
- Sanni, O. (2010a): "Why do Nigerian leaders evade tax?" In Nigerian Tribune. Friday July 30. Retrieved on Saturday September 24, 2011 from <http://www.tribune.com.ng/index.php/taxation/8957-why-do-nigerian-leaders-evade-tax>
- Sanni, O. (2010b): "Nigerian government and tax evasion". In Nigerian Tribune. Friday September 10. Retrieved on Monday June 4, 2012 from <http://www.tribune.com.ng/index.php/taxation/10859-nigerian-government-and-tax-evasion>
- Sapovadia, V. K. (2004): "Optimizing Decision Making System and Capacity: Lessons from Empirical Study of Selected Successful and Collapsed Major Cooperations in India". ICA Research Conference. January. Retrieved from http://works.bepress.com/vrajul_sapovadia/11/
- Sheppard, L. (2010): "Tax & Finance: Transfer Pricing as tax avoidance". Retrieved on Thursday August 18, 2011 from <http://www.forbes.com/2010/06/24/tax-finance-multinational-economics...>
- Stovall, O. S., Neill, J. D. and Perkins, D. (2004): "Corporate Governance, Internal Decision Making and the Invisible Hand". In Journal of Business Ethics Online. Abstract. Retrieved on July 6, 2010 from <http://www.springerlink.com/content/j5745288j2094577/>
- Tanzi, V. and Zee, H. (2001): "Tax Policy for Developing Countries." March. Retrieved on Sunday September 25, 2011 from

<http://www.imf.org/external/pubs/ft/issues/issues27/index.htm>

Tax Audit Headquarters (2005): *Tax Audit Guide*. Abuja: Federal Inland Revenue Service

Tax Justice Network (2005): "Transfer Pricing". Retrieved on Friday September 2, 2011 from http://www.taxjustice.net/cms/front_content.php?idcat=139

Tax World (1999): "A History of Taxation." April 7. Retrieved on Wednesday August 31, 2011 from <http://www.taxworld.org/History/TaxHistory.html>

Tella, A., Ayeni, C. O. and Popoola, S. O. (2007): "Work Motivation, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment of Library Personnel in Academic and Research Libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria". Retrieved on Friday September 23, 2011 from <http://unllib.unl.edu/LPP/tella2.pdf>